

LIGHTWEIGHT CRYPTOGRAPHY IN IOT NETWORKS

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Abstract: With the advent of advanced technology, the IoT has made possible the connection of numerous devices that can collect vast volumes of data. Hence, the demands for IoT security are paramount. Cryptography is being used to secure the authentication, confidentiality, data integrity, and access control of networks. However, due to the many constraints of IoT devices, traditional cryptographic protocols are no longer suited to all IoT environments, such as the smart city. As a result, researchers have been proposing various lightweight cryptographic algorithms and protocols to secure data on IoT networks. This paper discusses state-of-the-art lightweight cryptographic protocols for IoT networks and presents a comparative analysis of popular contemporary ciphers. In doing so, it has classified the most current algorithms into two parts: symmetric and asymmetric lightweight cryptography. Additionally, we evaluate several recently developed block cipher, and stream cipher algorithms in terms of their security. In the final section of this paper, we address the changes that need to be made and suggest future research topics.

Keywords: Lightweight cryptography, Block cipher, Stream cipher, Elliptic curve cipher, Internet of Things (IoT), Security

INTRODUCTION

The IoT objective is to allow things to be communicated anywhere, anytime, with anything, preferably applying any network or service. In the last few years, the IoT has grown exponentially and now occupies our lives in areas as diverse as cities, agriculture, hospitals, the environment, homes, roads, etc. IoT end devices are usually

equipped with different types of sensors and actuators, which collect numerous data and send the accumulated data through cyberspace to monitor, analyze, control, and reach various conclusions [1]. Most of these data are real-time data and help us make correct decisions in different service domains. However, this Internet-driven raw data needs to be transferred securely and switched to human-understandable information to gather knowledge and use this knowledge in various domains such as the smart city, agriculture, the environment, interactive transport, and electricity grids.

The smart city is one example of an IoT domain that has security problems that can be overcome by improving cryptography. Seventy percent of smart city services are currently provided in three fields: traffic, safety, and power [2]. Figure 1 shows the leading smart city model around the globe. The United Nations Population Fund indicates that more than half of the world's population now resides in a city. By 2050, this is expected to increase to about 68% [3]. In China, more than 200 smart city developments are in progress [4]. However, smart city domains create numerous security and privacy challenges due to various weaknesses in each layer of a smart city's network architecture. For example, in 2015, approximately 230,000 Ukrainian residents experienced an extended period of power interruption when intruders hacked into the electricity grid [5]. The IoT plays a crucial role in predicting and managing natural disasters such as bushfires, earthquakes, hurricanes, and tsunamis. Various IoT sensors can help avoid and control damage to life and the environment from forest fires. The sensors can be installed around the edges of the forest and can continuously monitor the temperature and carbon content in the region. In cases of emergency, the IoT can aid an immediate response by preparing and distributing the environment report. The 2019–2020 bushfires in Australia burned 46 million acres and cost 2.9 billion USD [6]. According to United Nations Food and Agriculture, the world will need 70% more food production in 2050 [7]. Smart agriculture will play a decisive factor in this growing market. For instance, in Chile, using remote sensors reduces 70% of the water requirement in blueberry production [8].

Figure-1. Major services in a smart city network

The network layer, also called the transit layer, processes and securely routes or transmits data throughout the IoT infrastructure. This layer uses different protocols like Zigbee, Bluetooth, IR, and 6LowPan for data transmission. For further processing and action, the network layer depends on the middleware layer. Following are some of the different possible attacks in this layer.

Eavesdropping: Eavesdropping is a passive attack and extracts the message contents from network broadcastings. It snoops, captures, and sniffs out broadcasted data and initiates different attacks or steals different critical information.

Device cloning attacks: As IoT devices are easily accessible from the network, an intruder can create a clone of the device and compromise IoT network infrastructure using these devices.

Spoofing attacks: Devices are connected to the network either directly or through a gateway in the IoT structure. An attacker can physically capture the node or gateways and can replace or reprogram them with malicious code. Edge devices and gateways must be authenticated, and the data should be encrypted to prevent this kind of attack.

DDoS attacks: IoT devices are exposed to these attacks as the IoT architecture uses heterogeneous and resource-constrained nodes. Firstly, an attacker captures the

device's credentials and then gets access to the gateways/devices. A hacker uses network information to explore the IoT devices and can initiate a DoS attack by sending fake packets up and down the entire system.

Key attack: Some devices have pre-shared keys that are hard-coded within the code. Hence, the intruder can easily capture this information.

Traffic analysis: Traffic analysis is another passive attack that can retrieve valuable information from the network traffic, such as source and destination details from the header of the transmitted communications.

Brute-force attack: This is known as an exhaustive search. This is a cryptographic hack that depends on predicting possible patterns of a targeted password to discover the correct password.

Man-in-the-middle attacks: Due to the heterogeneous nature of IoT architecture, an intruder can secretly capture communications between two parties to eavesdrop or modify traffic travelling between them. Attackers may capture personal information, login credentials, disrupt communications, and corrupt data.

Sinkhole attacks: In this type of attack, an adversary generates sinkholes to attract traffic flow from IoT devices. The attacker can later reroute the network traffic to devices other than the destination gateway.

Block cipher is a symmetric cipher where a complete block of data is processed simultaneously. Lightweight block ciphers are used in two distinct styles of networks: Substitution-permutation networks (SPN) and Feistel networks (FN). A Feistel structure is designed to have the same circuit for encryption and decryption, which keeps the costs down. Feistel structures use the same program code for encryption and decryption procedures, which ensures low memory requirements. The SPN is faster without a key schedule, but this makes the system vulnerable to attacks. The SPN structure is more suitable for security because of lesser execution requirements, and it has a lower power expenditure.

Key size, block size, structure type, and the encryption/ decryption rounds are the primary considerations to evaluate a lightweight block cipher. Thangamani and Murugappan recommended that a lightweight algorithm must focus on the three challenges: minimal memory, low power intake, and address insufficient security. Zhao, Yan, and Li recommended that a lightweight algorithm should have a small block size of 32–64 bits compared to the conventional 64 and 128 bits block size.

Figure-2. Classification of recently developed lightweight cryptography algorithms.

Encryption is done using LED, PRESENT and RECTANGLE S-Box. However, the SPECK algorithm is also used for key scheduling. The proposed system used a 64 bits key of plain data to encrypt and perform an XOR operation with a 128 bits schedule key. The LED cipher used the typical key algorithm, which is not that resistant to key attacks. However, the 128 bits SPECK key schedule algorithm is used in the proposed system, which gives it a lightweight nature and secures it from various key attacks. This advanced system uses a 64-bit block plain text XOR with 128 bits key that maintains its robustness. The proposed algorithm is lightweight and secure from various key attacks but does not resist other security attacks.

Noura, Couturier, Pham, and Chehab proposed a lightweight stream cipher scheme (LSC) to reach a high level of security. This is based on the dynamic key-dependent method. This system includes only a few simple operations that reduce costs. It involves cryptographic primitives, which change in a dynamic, lightweight manner for each input block. Security and performance studies confirm that the proposed cipher attains a high level of effectiveness and robustness, making it suitable for resource-restricted IoT devices. It uses 128, 192, and 256 bit secret keys with a nonce. This algorithm is a combination of CR4, Pseudo-random number generator (PRNG), and Linear feedback shift register (LFSR) with 12 to 14 rounds. This algorithm shows high periodicity, low energy consumption and is resistant to statistical, algebraic, and brute-force attacks. However, it is not adequate for disclosure and de-synchronization attacks.

Shantha and Arockiam designed the SAT_Jo system, which is based on the substitution-permutation network with a new lightweight block cipher that is appropriate for tag-based functions of the IoT. This system computes a 4×4 S-box by 2^4 orders of the Galois field. This design is based on the SPN of a block cipher with DES and PRESENT and involves 31 rounds. It uses a 64 bit block and 80 bit key size. This system presents an adequate level of security to the resource-constrained nodes of tag-based applications. The researchers found that it offers a better balance

between performance, resource requirements and security for resource-constrained IoT systems.

Recently developed cryptography can be split into two types, symmetric and asymmetric. Block cipher and stream cipher represent a symmetric algorithm, whereas ECC represents the asymmetric cipher. Symmetric ciphers use reduced key length compared to the asymmetric algorithm. Hence, they are vulnerable to security attacks because of their less complex nature. Asymmetric ciphers use more complexity to secure IoT network communications, but the larger key length makes them slower. Studying these crucial considerations is necessary to create an algorithm that will use less power, decrease complexity, take less time, and adequate security to low-end IoT devices. Hash functions denote another cipher besides symmetric and asymmetric. The function, also called message digests, is a keyless cipher. Hashing supports integrity instead of confidentiality services. This is a one-way cipher and cannot decrypt to plain text. It has two parts – the message and the message digest. Any alterations to the message would create a different message digest. Some of the lightweight hash functions are LNHASH, PHOTON, HVH and SPONGENT. Symmetric cipher Message authentication codes (MAC) provide authenticity and integrity in the data transfer process. It generates a tag from the message and a secret key. This can be used to verify the message integrity, which has been done intentionally or accidentally during transmission. Light MAC and CHASKEY are examples of the lightweight MAC cipher. We are not discussing the hash function and MAC in this chapter as we will focus more on other symmetric ciphers like block, stream and ECC ciphers.

CONCLUSION

In the above, we introduced the lightweight cryptographies applicable to the resource-constrained environments of IoT by focusing on the ones developed by NEC. Lightweight cryptography also requires consideration of the key management functions and operations in actual applications. NEC is therefore promoting R&D for the practical realization of a lightweight cryptography library by also covering updating

and exchanging of keys. We are also conducting research into lightweight cryptography in key exchange based on public key encryption. In the future, we intend to continue to contribute to secure IoT systems via research into the cryptographic technologies as discussed in this paper.

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